

UNDERTREES: Creating knowledge for UNDERstanding ecosystem seRvicEs of agroforEstry systems through a holistic methodological framework

UNDERTREES

AGROFORESTRY RESEARCH

Deliverable D3.1 – Report on the methodological framework at field scale

Deliverable number: 3.1

Deliverable title: Report on the methodological framework at field scale

WP number: 3

Lead beneficiary: SSSA

Deliverable type: Report

Dissemination level: Public

Due date: 31/12/2022

Issue date: 29/12/2022

Author(s): Alberto Mantino (SSSA)

Reviewer(s): Susanne Schnabel (UEX)

Version: 1.0

Status:

Project acronym:	UNDERTREES
Project full title:	Creating knowledge for UNDERstanding ecosystem seRvicEs of agroforEstry systems through a holistic methodological framework
Call identifier:	H2020-MSCA-RISE-2019
Start date:	1 January 2020
End date:	30 June 2025
Grant agreement n°:	872384

Document history

Version	Date	Author	Partner	Description
1	29/12/2022	Alberto Mantino	SSSA	

Element	ES Section*	ES Division*	Group	Class	Indicator	Methodology	Level (Field/Farm and Landscape)	
Air	Regulation & Maintenance	Regulation of physical, chemical	Air quality	GHGs emission	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, NH ₃ , CFC content	Eddy covariance tower	F / L	
				GHGs emission	GWP - Global warming potential	LCA	F / L	
Soil	Regulation & Maintenance	Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Soil quality for agricultural production (food and feed)	Fertility	Nutrient content: Cation exchange capacity, total N, exch. P, K, Ca, Mg, Na	Laboratory	F / L	
					Organic matter content	Laboratory	F / L	
				Water availability	Plant available water	Estimation + Lab	F / L	
					Soil thickness	Field	F	
					Thickness of Ah horizon	Field	F	
			Soil conservation – physical	Compaction	Bulk density, soil fractions, aggregate stability	Lab	F	
				Present erosion	Erosion features (rills, gullies, sheetwash)	Field observation	F	
				Slope instability	Signs of gravity movements	Field observation	F	
				Soil conservation – biological and chemical	Microarthropod community	QBS index	Laboratory: extraction system	F
					Microbioma	Microbial communities	DNA extraction	F
				Microbial activity	CO ₂ flux in soil, microbial biomass C and microbial respiration	Field: flux chamber	F	
	Provisioning	Water	Water availability for agricultural production incl	Climate condition	Monthly rainfall	Field + official data	F / L	
					Aridity index	Precip/ET (average annual mean)	F / L	
					Potential ET	Penman-Monteith	F / L	
					Evapotranspiration			
	Provisioning	Water	Water availability for animal and human consumption	Infrastructure provision	Water ponds: Total max. volume/surface area (m ³ / km ²)	Field + image analysis	F / L	
					Groundwater (wells)	Farmer interview	F	
				Management capacity	Adaptation strategies to droughts	Farmer interview	F	
				Water needs	Livestock water consumption	Estimation based on animal type and density	F	
			Water quality	Water quality	Chemical analysis	F		
Crop and pasture	Provisioning	Biomass	Cultivated terrestrial plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Food provision	Grain Yield	Field measurements, remote sensing or database	F / L	
					Quality of the production	Chemical analysis	F	
				Feed provision	Forage Yield	Field measurements or database	F / L	
					Nutritive value	Chemical analysis	F	
				Residue or by-products	Yield	Field measurements or database	F	
					Nutritive value (for animal)	Chemical analysis	F	
				Crop rotation	Crop species	Farmer Survey	F	
				Use of agro-chemicals	consumption of pesticides	Farmer Survey	F	
Tree	Provisioning	Biomass	Cultivated terrestrial plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Timber provision	Timber yield	Field measurements, remote sensing or database	F / L	
					Timber quality	Chemical analysis	F	
				Biomass provision	Biomass yield	Field measurements, remote sensing or database	F / L	
					biomass quality	Chemical analysis	F	
				Food provision	Yield	Field measurements or database	F / L	
					Quality of the production	Chemical analysis	F	
				Feed provision	Yield	Field measurements or database	F / L	
					Nutritive value	Chemical analysis	F	
				Residue or by-products	Yield	Field measurements or database	F / L	
					Nutritive value (for animal)	Chemical analysis	F	
				Provisioning and maintenance of diversity and heterogeneity	Tree diversity	Tree species	Field observation or database	F / L
		Animal	Regulation & Maintenance	Biomass	Reared animals for	Food provision	Yield	Animal measurements or database
	Quality of the production					Chemical analysis	F	
Reared animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Manure				Quantity in terms of N, P, K and C	Field measurement and Chemical analysis	F	
	Reared animals for				Animal Welfare	Hair cortisol	Sampling and chemical analysis	F
						Heat stress	Thermal indices (THI, BGHI)	F / L
Human	Provisioning					Maintenance and improvement of economic feasibility	Owners	Quality of life
		Generational replacement (renewal)	Questionary, Survey or Focus Group	F				
		Employees	Quality of life	Questionary, Survey or Focus Group			F	
			Generational replacement (renewal)	Questionary, Survey or Focus Group			F	
		Economic balance	Initial investment cost	Questionary, Survey or Focus Group			F	
			Maintenance costs (annual)	Questionary, Survey or Focus Group			F	
	Sales of agricultural products		Questionary, Survey or Focus Group	F				
				Sales of non- agricultural products	Questionary, Survey or Focus Group	F		
		Regulation & Maintenance	Regulation of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Fire protection	Fire protection	Presence of Fire	Questionary, Survey or Focus Group	F / L